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Integrated Child Development Services - Strengthening Human Security in Tamil Nadu

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Abstract:

Integrated Child Development Services in the spectrum of health security and social development at the grassroots. The ICDS through the anganwadi units serves as a vital public health infrastructure in every gram panchayat or village. The ICDS at the grassroots-level of the healthcare system assumes

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greater significance underscoring the critical role of ensuring good health to pregnant women and children. The role of ICDS in reducing the maternal and infant mortality is indispensable, by providing antenatal and postnatal care serves as a key indicator in understanding the health infrastructure effectiveness, and robustness at the grassroots. The primary objectives of the study are to analysis and evaluate the ICDS through its Anganwadi centres. By examining factors such as Availability, Accessibility, Performance, and awareness, the study aims to explore the gaps in the crucial health service for a better community well-being and resilience. Through this lens, the study aims to contribute to ICDS effectiveness and the broader discourse on health security in Tamil Nadu.

Introduction:

The Integrated Child Development Service (ICDS), launched in 1975, has been a core scheme in delivering health and nutrition and, importantly, in shaping early childhood development interventions nationwide. The services' impacts differ from state to state due to implementation variability, human resource challenges, inadequate infrastructure, resource constraints, and a lack of community participation. The variability in implementation has led to varying differences among the states in delivering these services, impacting the quality of life and improvement in the Human Development Index. The Anganwadi centres at the grassroots level deliver health and nutritional services. The centres are located in every village, ensuring access to the rural population. The Anganwadi are a cornerstone of social welfare and development, ensuring equal access to health and education for all and empowering marginalised communities. The services also ensure proper maternal and reproductive health for women. Pregnant and lactating mothers receive antenatal care, postnatal care, and supplementary nutrition. Proper counselling for mothers on various healthcare needs is given occasionally. ICDS has successfully reduced maternal and infant mortality rates through its resilient interventions on health and nutrition.

Tamil Nadu has been a high-performing state in reducing child malnutrition, improving maternal health, promoting early childhood development, and achieving broad immunisation coverage through its innovative approach, which includes high community participation and robust monitoring from grassroots to top-level

administration. Assessing nutrition and health interventions at the grassroots level from the beneficiaries and relevant stakeholders will provide state-specific insights for more effective service delivery.

Study Background:

Tamil Nadu has been one of the top-performing states in delivering services through ICDS, and assessing its impact is vital for more effective delivery. As part of extensive Human Security Research, this study aims to understand the reach of effective health and nutritional interventions in ensuring the health and food security of vulnerable populations, primarily in rural areas of the state. The study will highlight areas that require more attention for long-term sustainability and a resilient service delivery system. Evaluating the effectiveness of Anganwadi service delivery is crucial in addressing broader concerns related to human security.

The study area comprises nine districts with 18 blocks and 72 villages. The rationale of the study area is based on the last published Tamil Nadu Human Development Index 2017, which included three districts from the top, middle, and bottom performing areas. The household survey comprises a total of 1,940 respondents in each village, utilising non-probability purposive sampling to target the population below the poverty line, ensuring an adequate understanding of the primary beneficiaries during time period of 2023-2024.

Study Population - District wise

District	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Ariyalur	239	12.3	12.3
Cuddalore	202	10.4	22.7
Dindigul	228	11.8	34.5
Kanniyakumari	218	11.2	45.7
Namakkal	195	10.1	55.8
Perambalur	214	11.0	66.8
Theni	214	11.0	77.8
Thoothukudi	213	11.0	88.8
Virudhunagar	217	11.2	100.0
	1940	100.0	

Components of the Study:

The paper aims to study the significant aspects of understanding the ICDS at the grassroots through four key integrals: Availability, Accessibility, Performance, and awareness about the scheme. The above-mentioned aspects will provide an overview of the ICDS interventions in the state, offering a broader perspective on human security.

To comprehend the services', reach to the people, the availability of an Anganwadi Centre in their locality is crucial. Several government services are inaccessible to the rural population due to accessibility issues. Geographical constraints and a lack of local administration intent are significant issues in delivering the services. This study aims to understand the availability of services for beneficiaries in terms of spatial access to ICDS services from their locality or home. Many services do not reach the intended beneficiaries due to the non-availability of the service-providing grassroots institution within their reach.

Anganwadi Availability

Availability	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	104	5.4	5.4	5.4
Yes	1836	94.6	94.6	100.0
Total	1940	100.0	100.0	

Majority of the population (94.6%) have access to an anganwadi with its availability in their reach and only (5.4%) have responded that, absence of anganwadi in their locality and this non-availability leading to non-acquirement of service. The cumulative percentage confirms and reflects the overall distribution of Anganwadi availability. Accessibility to avail the services is another important determinant in services delivery to the population.

Accessibility can be understood in terms of spatial i.e. location or distance and non-spatial factors such as economic, political, social, and institutional facilitation, etc. also influence the individuals in accessing the services. In spite of availability, many services do not reach the beneficiaries due to issues in accessibility, for a developed state, accessibility to its schemes for the population is the key for effective governance. Understanding the accessibility from the target population is essential for enhancing the governance.

ICDS Facilities Aailed

Districts	Facility Aailed		Total
	No	Yes	
Ariyalur	155	84	239
Cuddalore	182	20	202
Dindigul	124	104	228
Kanniyakumari	73	145	218
Namakkal	98	97	195
Perambalur	161	53	214
Theni	125	89	214
Thoothukudi	127	86	213
Virudhunagar	157	60	217
Total	1202	738	1940

Only 38% of the study population have accessed Anganwadi services. It highlights the need to expand its outreach and service delivery to the population. 62% of the surveyed population have not utilised or accessed the services due to a lack of need, access to private services, lack of awareness, dissatisfaction, or non-spatial factors.

The performance of the ICDS anganwadi centre needs to be analysed in order to understand its efficiency and accessibility. Evaluation of the centre's performance from the targeted beneficiaries is essential to understand the impact it has created in enhancing the quality of life and ensuring the health security of women and children. However, various factors affect the functionality of the centres, such as a lack of funding, insufficient staff, and limited resources, but their impact is still profound on rural society.

Performance of Anganwadi Centres

District	Average	Bad	Excellent	Good	Not Applicable	Worst	Total
Ariyalur	18	1	2	63	155	0	239
Cuddalore	2	0	0	17	182	1	202
Dindigul	58	0	10	36	124	0	228
Kanniyakumari	3	1	83	58	73	0	218
Namakkal	20	2	18	56	98	1	195
Perambalur	10	3	3	37	161	0	214
Theni	2	0	20	67	125	0	214
Thoothukudi	3	1	27	55	127	0	213
Virudhunagar	11	1	15	32	157	1	217
Total	127	9	178	421	1202	3	1940

The table presents the performance of anganwadi centres district-wise for an in-depth understanding. A total of 62% of responses across all districts fall under 'Not Applicable', which implies that either they have not accessed the facility as mentioned earlier. Only minimal negative performance feedback, at 0.7%, including the worst options, indicates less dissatisfaction among the targeted population. 31.0% of respondents provided positive responses regarding the services, showcasing their satisfaction and reflecting the efficacy of the services.

Another important factor to be studied is the awareness about the services; people have not utilised many schemes in India due to a lack of awareness. The government has taken various initiatives to raise awareness about the schemes and benefits through various media, as well as an awareness campaign supported by the local government. However, the lack of awareness about schemes persists due to the inadequate dissemination of information, limited campaigns, restricted access to information, and administrative barriers.

The ICDS services have been a longstanding initiative with reach to every village in the nation. However, it is essential to raise awareness about them among the targeted rural population for effective interventions. A lack of awareness has been a primary concern, as several schemes have not reached their intended

beneficiaries. The lack of community participation is a significant factor contributing to a lack of awareness about government schemes. The role of local government is crucial in creating community participation for every welfare scheme initiated by the government, ensuring the overall reach and coverage of the targeted population.

Awareness on ICDS and Schemes

ICDS Awareness	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	1353	69.7	69.7	69.7
Yes	587	30.3	30.3	100.0
Total	1940	100.0	100.0	

The table above indicates that 69.7% of the population reported being unaware of ICDS services and schemes, whereas 30.3% are aware of the programs. The awareness gap on the ICDS highlights that a majority of the study population may not have utilised the available services due to various factors. This huge gap in awareness will undermine the effectiveness of the scheme in attaining its goals and the delivery of services at large. The table underscores the importance of more campaigns to make the public aware of the benefits of the services. Awareness is a critical component for utilising ICDS services and enhancing efforts to increase participation and access to the service for social development.

Sustainability Framework for implementation:

A sustainable implementation plan or framework is crucial for a scheme to achieve its goal, and its impact can be seen in society. The gaps in implementation as a whole lead to inefficiency in the services, ultimately resulting in the program's failure.

The study aims to provide an implementation framework for more effective delivery, despite the high impact of the present ICDS schemes in Tamil Nadu. For a more effective implementation at the grassroots level, the role of the local government, specifically Gram Panchayats, is indispensable. Apart from following the procedures, proactive measures, awareness, grievance redressal, and feedback mechanisms need to be ensured by the local governments for a result-oriented

implementation of the scheme. Another important factor is the Local government's understanding of the problems in accessing government services and facilitating their availability. To understand the problem, the panchayats' proactivity and cohesion with the people are essential for the successful implementation and impact of the scheme. Inputs from the community on the issues and needs are crucial to be analysed for interventions at intervals. A fixed service delivery that fails to address the community's needs will not improve their standard of living or ensure their human security. Even though the policy formulation is centralised, the interventions can be decentralised according to the locality. The Gram Panchayat should address the root cause of the issue in service delivery apart from providing a temporary solution. Local government interventions at the grassroots level to address human security concerns directly will help build a resilient community, with the help of schemes that empower individuals by improving their standard of living.

Conclusion:

The role of ICDS is indispensable in ensuring the health security of adolescent girls and women through its services. Based on field observations in the nine districts, dependence on anganwadi services among the people is high, especially in rural areas. For women from low socioeconomic backgrounds, the service impact is high, ensuring their access to supplementary healthcare and nutrition programs. The impact of these services is a crucial variable in reducing maternal and infant mortality rates throughout the state. The prenatal and postnatal care for young mothers, along with access to nutritious food and vaccination for the infant since birth, has ensured the health security of the beneficiaries. Early childhood care and education shape early childhood development, shaping cognitive and emotional development along with socialisation. The role of anganwadi in reducing social disparities is significant, as it bridges the gaps in early childhood education and health among communities, irrespective of socioeconomic differences. Anganwadi primarily targets beneficiaries from rural and disadvantaged or vulnerable communities, ensuring access to maternal health and early education through its services. The centres also serve as a capacity-building hub among the community, addressing concerns regarding health, education, and social development effectively and building a resilient community, fostering social cohesion and community engagement. Anganwadi ensure social inclusivity and accessibility to vulnerable and marginalised communities. The reduction of maternal mortality rate, infant mortality rate, and reduction of malnutrition are the objectives of the ICDS through the anganwadi, and it has been successful in Tamil Nadu. Challenges such as a lack of resources, under funding, inadequate training for workers, and limited accountability are key areas that require attention and improvement. The gaps in implementation need to be addressed, as they are crucial for the effectiveness and sustainability of the initiative. The results highlight the need to raise awareness of the services and schemes, along with increasing accessibility for the people. The performance of the anganwadi is another essential component to be monitored and policies reformulated regularly according to the needs for effective development at the grassroots. If the gaps in implementation are addressed, the impact of the services will contribute to ensuring the health security and nutrition needs of the targeted beneficiaries. The role of local government, or the Gram Panchayat, in monitoring and evaluating the service and its impact among communities, along

with active engagement, is essential for successful service delivery. The ICDS, through the anganwadi, creates a profound impact in ensuring the human security of vulnerable communities, while also contributing to an equitable society and making vital contributions to the social transformation and development of communities.

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References:

- Balakrishnan, S. (2011) : Differently abled children and school education in Tamil Nadu a public policy study. *University of Madras*.
<https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/204231>
- Dr. Chhavi Bhatnagar. (2023) : Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) Scheme. *Global Books Organisation*.
- Harikrishna, B.N., Jothula, K.Y., Nagaraj, K., & Prasad, V.G. (2020) : Utilisation of Anganwadi services among pregnant women in rural Telangana: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 9(7), Article 7.
https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmmpc.jfmmpc_408_20
- *ICDS Striving for Holistic Development | Economic and Political Weekly*. (2019, December 6).
<https://www.epw.in/journal/2019/48/special-articles/icds-striving-holistic-development.html>
- Madhavi H, Singh HK, Bendigiri ND. (2011) : A study of utilization of Integrated Child Development Services(ICDS) scheme and beneficiaries-satisfaction in rural area of Gulbarga district. *Pravara Medical Review*, Vol. 3, Issue 3, 13.

- Rao, N. (2005) : Children's rights to survival, development, and early education in India: The critical role of the Integrated Child Development Services program. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 37(3), Article 3.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03168343>
- Sachdev, Y., & Dasgupta, J. (2001) : Integrated child development services (ICDS) scheme. *Medical Journal Armed Forces India*, 57(2), Article 2.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-1237\(01\)80135-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-1237(01)80135-0)
- *13.63 lakh Anganwadi Centres (AWCs) of the 14 lakh AWCs sanctioned across the country are operational as on 01.06.2018.* (2025, February 20).
<https://pib.gov.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=18121>